

D14.2 – Final report on the ARIADNEplus knowledge management system

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the activities carried out by the partners during the second half of the ARIADNEplus project within Work Package 14 (WP14 - JRA3 - *The ARIADNEplus knowledge management system*) and describes the results of the four WP14 tasks:

- Task 14.1 – Monitoring knowledge integration (JRA3.1)
- Task 14.2 – Application profiles (JRA3.2)
- Task 14.3 – Vocabularies and gazetteers (JRA3.3)
- Task 14.4 – Assessing the CRM extensions (JRA3.4)

The overall objectives of WP14 are presented in Section 2 while Sections 3, 4, 5 and 6 present the detailed work in Tasks 14.1, 14.2, 14.3 and 14.4 respectively. Work in WP14 is closely related to other work packages and more specifically to WP4 where the ARIADNEplus ontology and specific extensions, the application profiles, to specific sub-domains of archaeology and archaeological science, are being implemented. Deliverables of WP4 provide a detailed description of the AO-Cat (*D4.2 - Initial report on ontology implementation*) and the progress on the application profiles (*D4.4 - Final report on ontology implementation*, due at the end of the project). Whenever necessary, references to other deliverables will be provided.

Overall, the activities of WP14 were carried out successfully and with very good cooperation with other interlinked work packages such as WP4, 5, and 12. Activity Dash, integrated into the projects' infrastructure, was used to monitor the aggregation process, with 62 active workflows creating and recording the aggregation progress status of all the data providers. The development of the application profiles was carried out in close collaboration between the partners of 14.2 and 4.4 and led to the release of four stable fundamental application profiles for the specific research domains of inscriptions, marks, graffiti and other textual entities, ancient DNA analysis, heritage science scientific analysis and mortuary archaeology. The classes and properties that constitute each application profile are borrowed from existing ontological models or derived from them and are fully compatible with the AO-Cat general model and the CIDOC CRM, which form the backbone of ARIADNEplus.

Work on multilingual vocabularies was carried out in close collaboration with WP5 on vocabulary integration via mappings from partner vocabularies to the Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) and via the PeriodO framework for temporal periods (see also WP5 Deliverables and the User Manual for the ARIADNEplus Data Aggregation Pipeline). The assessment of the CRM extensions included testing integrated data from the fields of numismatics, epigraphies and mortuary archaeology. A semantic search demonstrator was built to query and test the numismatic and epigraphic data integrated to the item-level. The mapping of Thanados¹ database to the infrastructure was used to test the mortuary data AP.

¹ <https://thanados.net/>

2 Introduction and Objectives

The objectives of WP14 - JRA3 - *The ARIADNEplus knowledge management system* centre on four main tasks:

- define the ARIADNEplus semantic framework;
- define and build the ontologies required for ARIADNEplus;
- analyse, adapt and, if necessary, build the required Knowledge Organization Systems;
- assess the ARIADNE ontology extensions, and validate the work done in this work package, and in WP4 where implementation takes place.

This report presents details about the activities carried out during the second half of the ARIADNEplus project and the final results in each Task of the work package.

Section 3 presents the activities and results of Task 14.1. The objective of Task 14.1 is to monitor the aggregation process. The aggregation process is described in the document “Data Aggregation Pipeline: User Guide”² and in the deliverable D12.4 Final report on data integration. It is a workflow that involves the use of several tools to perform a set of activities and tasks, in a certain order, by several partners and requires close monitoring. To do this, we designed and implemented Activity Dash, a dashboard that supports monitoring of the aggregation process, as displayed schematically in Figure 1. Activity Dash allows a group of users to keep track of the whole aggregation process. It provides information about which resources have been uploaded/mapped/transformed and when. It also provides a collaborative environment allowing multiple users to work within the same workspace simultaneously.

Figure 1: Activity Dash monitors activities and tasks of the aggregation workflow.

² <https://data.d4science.net/z5T4>

Section 4 presents the activities of Task 14.2. The primary purpose of task 14.2 is the coordination of activities related to the definition of application profiles. All the activities of this task have been carried out in close collaboration with Task 4.4. The results of these activities, including the requirements and the application profiles that have been defined, are presented in detail in *D4.4 - Final report on ontology implementation*, due on December 2022. In Section 4 of this report we provide a general overview of the application profiles that have been developed.

Section 5 presents the activities of Task 14.3 on vocabularies and gazetteers. Work on multilingual vocabularies overlaps to some extent with work for WP5 on vocabulary integration via mappings from Partner vocabularies to the Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT). These mappings contribute to a multilingual vocabulary resource compiled from different sources. Section 5 presents the work that has been done to extract, convert and combine multilingual resources from Wikidata, Getty AAT and other relevant sources. Moreover, we present temporal integration via the PeriodO framework for temporal periods. The work on vocabulary integration is detailed in the User Manual for the ARIADNEplus Data Aggregation Pipeline and D5.2 First report on Data Infrastructure update and extension.

Finally, section 6 presents the results from the assessment of the CRM extensions through three use cases: numismatics, inscriptions and mortuary data. Assessing the CRM extensions was a process across several activities and WPs: the specific Task 4 in WP14; in WP 4, Task 4.4 where the definition of Application Profiles for archaeological subdomains was completed and where CIDOC CRM extensions for field surveys have been discussed; in WP12, Task 12.4 during the item-level data integration of archaeological subdomains that required more detailed mappings.

All sections follow the same structure providing an overview and the actual work achieved by the task.

3 Monitoring knowledge integration (Activity Dash)

Activity Dash is an online web application used for tracking workflow processes in the ARIADNEplus project. Its functionality combines a workflow manager and tracker, a collaborative environment and a notification mechanism for all stakeholders. Its architectural design, implementation method and functional model, are described in detail in deliverable D14.1 Mid-term interim report on the ARIADNEplus knowledge management system (<https://zenodo.org/record/4926526#.Y2OcPnZByid>). This document aims at providing details on how it was validated, improved, expanded and used by end users, during the second half of ARIADNEplus project.

Activity Dash offers a modern environment for tracking progress done on workflow activities performed by different people. It is capable of serving the needs of many different projects, each of which might have many workflows, making it a generic tool suitable for serving different needs and targets.

The workspace environment offered by the system, presents the workflow divided into activities, which are further divided into tasks. Each workflow has an owner who is in charge of anything happening within the workflow itself. The workflow owner assigns a single user to each activity or task as responsible. All these stakeholders are able to edit the parts of the workflow for which they are in charge simultaneously, while receiving changes applied from others on the fly. The whole synchronisation process is automatically applied by the system among all active workspace views. Activities within the workflow can also hold associations. This is mainly done when some activity depends on the completeness of other activities. Similar associations can exist between tasks of a single activity as well. The system is capable of automatically informing stakeholders, under specific circumstances, about the completeness of some activity (or task respectively) or when a new assignment or dismissed assignment has been implemented.

The same environment allows users to exchange information and feedback through the form of single messages or whole conversations of multiple participants with respect to certain workflows, activities or small tasks. That information is well organised across the system and properly delivered to end-users through a simple and friendly graphical interface. Stakeholders can receive notifications either through internal messages or via email.

3.1 Usage of the system in the project

In the first two years of the project, Activity Dash (AD) was tested by a small group of people (for validation purposes), and then made available to all D4Science users, 129 of which were successfully registered in the system and were able to use it for recording the progress status of 63 workflows.

The ARIADNEplus project and a template workflow have been defined in AD. For every provider of data to the ARIADNE Infrastructure, a template-based workflow was set up and tasks assigned to relevant people. This allowed users to track the progress of their task through the interface. Currently, a total of 26 workflows have been fully tracked and another 37 in the tracking process.

Moreover, the collaboration environment offered by the system was systematically used by stakeholders, allowing the exchange of messages regarding issues and work to be done to complete the workflows (see Figure 2). These discussions usually took the form of conversation among several users around the workflow of interest. The system managed to keep the information in a well-organised way, and notify the stakeholders through email when a new message was exchanged. The picture below shows a small piece of such a “conversation” from Activity Dash. Each conversation is associated with a workflow and includes a direct shortcut.

Figure 2: AD collaboration environment.

3.2 Functional model expansion

The system was used under real conditions; assistance was offered where necessary and issues and bugs were uncovered and resolved. Additionally, the real use cases revealed further requirements which were covered by expanding and improving the current functional model. From these improvements, two completely new features were added. The first is a separate tree view of the workflow where the user is involved, allowing easy and direct access. The second major addition is the ability to export/import workflows in a JSON format, in case it is needed (i.e. migration to another server, local workflow backups, etc.). Table 1 shows the final functional model of the system, with the new additions highlighted in blue.

Security	
F01	The system is secured by a powerful and highly customisable authentication and access-control framework, which is mainly used for authenticating users, and granting them access to URLs (services and views), according to their roles.
F02	The JSON Web Token (JWT), is used to provide a compact and self-contained way for securely transmit information between parties, with optional signature and/or encryption.
F03	Role Based Access Control (RBAC) and Data Ownership are combined to provide the required user permissions and regulations.
F04	The system provides a registration mechanism for the new users, which also requires administrator's approval before gaining access.
Environment	
F05	The system is accessed through the web, using any new modern browser.
F06	Provides a simple, easy and friendly environment to the end-user.
F07	Provides good performance and makes use of web caching, where appropriate.
F08	Provides a dynamic UI environment that depends on user roles and ownership.
F09	The system is fully configurable, providing better flexibility.
F10	The system is fault tolerant, which means that it is capable of properly handling errors and remain functional after any error recovery.
F11	The system notifies end-users when a functional error occurs.
Administration	
F12	The system allows users to manage their own information.
F13	The system provides full user administration management.
F14	The system provides full workflow administration management.
F15	The system provides advanced messaging capabilities to the administrators, along with the appropriate environment to manage them.
F16	The system organizes the workflows into projects, which are also managed by the administrator.
Workspace	
F17	The system allows end-users to define their own preferences in certain functionality or parts of the system.
F18	The system presents the workflows as a set of activities, which may or may not be divided into tasks.
F19	The system allows users to create relationships between activities within the same workflow or tasks within the same activity in the form of dependencies.
F20	The system allows users to simultaneously work within the same workspace, editing or expanding the same workflow, and automatically sync all the actions as required.
F21	The system allows users to clone workflows or tasks.
F22	The system provides a silence mode for each workflow, which stops all notifications when an activity or task is completeness, or due to the creation of a new assignment/dismissal (very convenient after cloning and then editing a workflow).
F23	The system always asks for user permission before applying actions that cannot be undone.

F24	The system prevents users from making mistakes and provides directions and tooltips guiding end-users.
Notifications & Messages	
F25	The system provides a means of user notification, which is utilised either by the system itself or other users.
F26	The system provides two different means of notification, which are internal notification messages, or emails (or both).
F27	The system allows users to provide feedback on activities processed by others, by exchanging single messages or whole conversations.
F28	The system automatically informs stakeholders when dependent activities are 100% complete within a workflow.
F29	The system automatically informs stakeholders when they are assigned or dismissed from an activity or task.
F30	The system provides feedback to the end-user on every action made.
Workflow Searching & Component Access	
F31	The system provides certain filters for searching the workflows based on either name, description, ownership or status (ongoing/complete), which can be combined all together.
F32	Different sorting capabilities are available in any searching results.
F33	A separate tree view to observe user's involvement in workflows, is available for any user. This view groups all workflows, activities and tasks where the user is assigned and provides shortcuts for direct access to them.
F34	Feedback internal messages or conversations, provide shortcuts for direct access to the respective workflow or activity.
F35	Feedback emails sent to users by others, also include shortcut links for direct access to the respective workflow or activity.
Import Export	
F36	Import & export capabilities are provided by the system for the workflows.

Table 1: Activity Dash functional model.

Activity Dash was presented at an official online ARIADNEplus workshop, conducted on 10 February 2021, under the title "Activity Dash Tutorial". The presentation described the purpose of the tool, its design, organisational model and features. It included a live demo, during which its main components were explained and it was shown how to use it for tracking workflow activities and providing feedback. The presentation was recorded and the recording was made available through D4Science to all members.

Even though the ARIADNEplus project has almost reached to an end, Activity Dash will continue to be improved, expanded and maintained for internal or other project usage, since it has proved to be a useful tool for organising and tracking the work done.

4 Application Profiles

4.1 Overview

The primary purpose of Task 14.2 is the coordination of activities related to the definition of application profiles. All the activities of this task have been carried out in close collaboration with task 4.4. Application profiles can be seen as sets of entities used to model the data of specific research domains. The classes and properties that constitute each application profile are usually borrowed from existing ontological models or derived from them, and are typically arranged in coherent structures so as to keep compatibility with the AO-Cat general model and the CIDOC CRM, which is the reference ontology of ARIADNEplus.

The work of creating application profiles has been undertaken by 14 special interest groups charged with defining the specific requirements of each sub-domain of task 4.4, designing the classes and properties required for the modelling of the specific entities of each research discipline. The groups were also in charge of surveying, collecting, and managing multilingual domain thesauri and vocabularies necessary for describing domain-specific information.

The results of these activities, including the requirements and the application profiles that have been defined, are presented in detail in the D4.4 Final report on ontology implementation. Table 2 presents a summary of all the application profiles developed:

Subtask	Application Profile	Current Version	Description
ARIADNEplus catalogue	AO-Cat	1.1.10	AP for the representation of the resources in the ARIADNE Catalogue. It is described in D4.1 Initial report on dataset integration https://zenodo.org/record/4916262#.Y3TuenZByic and D4.3
Ancient DNA data (4.4.2)	aDNA AP	v1.0	The aDNA application profile is designed to describe the aDNA wetlab methodologies integrated with the contextual information regarding the samples. It is described in D4.2 https://zenodo.org/record/4916299#.Yanxe9BByid
Heritage science data (4.4.4, 4.4.5)	CRMhs AP	1.0	The CRMhs application profile is specifically designed for the encoding of information produced in the domain of Inorganic Materials Study, Dating, and in general for all types of data deriving from Heritage

Subtask	Application Profile	Current Version	Description
			Science research. (https://data.d4science.net/ngRG)
Inscriptions, marks and graffiti (4.4.13)	CRMtex	v1.1	CRMtex, the CIDOC CRM extension for the description of textual entities, has proved to be the ideal tool for the description of inscriptions, marks and graffiti. It is described in D4.2 https://zenodo.org/record/4916299#.Yanxe9BByid
Burials and mortuary data (4.4.14)	Mortuary AP	v1.2	The Mortuary Data AP is designed to model different types of burial data. https://zenodo.org/record/7252485#.Y3TwIXZByic
Palaeoanthropology (4.4.1) Environmental Archaeology (4.4.3) Field Survey (4.4.6) Metal Detector Surveys (4.4.7) Geospatial Data (4.4.10) Maritime and Underwater (4.4.11)	Not needed		The use of AO-Cat and the other Application Profiles developed by ARIADNEplus (e.g. CRMhs and aDNA) has proved to be sufficient for the encoding of information for these research domains. In some cases, entities from the CIDOC CRM ecosystem have been combination with extensive use of vocabularies and dedicated services (e.g.: Geographic systems) to implement a deeper integration.

Table 2: Application Profiles.

The following sections essentially provide a general overview of the four distinct application profiles developed, referring to the specific sections of D4.2 for more detailed information.

4.2 Heritage Science Application Profile

The CRMhs application profile is specifically designed for the encoding of information produced in the domain of Inorganic Materials Study (subtasks 4.4.4), Dating (subtask 4.4.5), and in general for all types of data deriving from Heritage Science research (CRMhs documentation is available at <https://data.d4science.net/ngRG>). CRMhs is the result of the activities of the scientific data working group specifically set up for the definition of this model and composed by partners from INFN, Cyl, HNM, PIN, OEAW and LNEC and is compatible with AO-Cat and with the whole CIDOC CRM ecosystem. A stable version of the model was already released during the first phase of ARIADNEplus and was extensively documented in Deliverable D4.2 (see Chapters 4.4 and 4.5, Chapter 5 and Appendix).

During the second part of the project, CRMhs profile was further extended and equipped with new entities for the description of scientific research protocols and their application methodologies. Each protocol, in fact, consists of a series of successive steps, each of which may be additionally expanded in (sub)steps linked together in sequence. CRMhs has released additional classes and properties to define step sequences, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Steps, sub-steps and sequences in Protocol definition of CRMhs.

Specific properties have also been defined to describe the features required to perform the protocol as a whole or within each step, such as its prescribed duration, the equipment and software needed to perform it, the methodologies to be used, and so on.

A flexible and user-friendly interface (THESPIAN-MASK) to encode information in CRMhs and AO-Cat format has also been developed by INFN for the cataloguing and storage of scientific data (<https://ch.cloud.cnaf.infn.it/metadatamask/>). THESPIAN-MASK also provides advanced features for Linked Open Data automatic acquisition and incorporation and to query remote thesauri and gazetteer (such as Getty AAT and PeriodO) for the rapid inclusion of conceptual and spatial information (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: THESPIAN-MASK interfaces for the encoding of scientific data in CRMhs and AO-Cat format.

During the last period, CRMhs was harmonised with the model developed for Bio-archaeology and ancient DNA (see next section) in order to define a complete framework for the description of all the data related to scientific activities that ARIADNEplus aims to integrate. The synergy between the two application profiles allows the encoding of very detailed scientific information, concerning instance analyses, the instrumentation used, the various activities of extraction and preparation of samples and all the other operations typical of the targeted research domains by using a combination of the most suitable entities of both the models.

4.3 Application Profile for ancient DNA

The ancient DNA application profile is designed to describe the ancient DNA wetlab methodologies (subtask 4.4.2) integrated with the contextual information regarding the samples. The aDNA application profile has been presented in D4.2 *Initial report on ontology implementation* (Section 6, Case Study 2). In this deliverable we give a short overview of the aDNA application profile and we present its harmonisation with CRMhs.

In the context of subtask 4.4.2, we analysed both the contextual information and the informal descriptions and formal metadata related to the scientific aDNA analysis workflow in order to produce a suitable application profile based on AO-Cat, CIDOC-CRM and the family of its compatible models. Projects currently running in the aDNA laboratory facilities of FORTH-IMBB were analysed. At the AO-Cat level of description, each project is described as an AO_Collection since it is an aggregation of resources. The properties of AO_Collection were found to be sufficient to describe aDNA projects at

a level of high abstraction. Modeling scientific workflows usually focuses on the digital data produced and ignores the large and complex experimental steps which are described only in the scientists' lab-books. In our approach, we analysed all steps of an aDNA project, starting from sampling, storage, DNA extraction, genomic library construction, sequencing, bioinformatics analyses, interpretation of the results and conclusions up to the publication of results.

Furthermore, we aligned the aDNA application profile with CRMhs, the heritage science model which is suitable for modelling scientific analyses (e.g. C14 or XRF) carried out on biological objects and cultural artefacts. Our goal is to specify an adequate form and extent of metadata that allows for effective control of provenance ensuring quality, validity, and FAIRness of data.

The aDNA application profile describes the aDNA wetlab services and links the sample data with contextual information. It is based on CIDOC-CRM and the family of its compatible models and is aligned with CRMhs and the Mortuary application profile (see Table 3):

- CIDOC CRM – The base model, version 6.2.1
- CRMsci – Scientific observation model, version 1.2.2
- CRMdig – Model for provenance metadata, version 3.2
- CRMarchaeo – Excavation model, version 1.4.1
- CRMpe – Model for Research Infrastructure management, the PARTHENOS Entity Model version 3.1.2
- CRMhs – Heritage Science model, version 1.0
- Mortuary AP, version 1.2

aDNA workflow main entities	AO-Cat	CRM/CRMpe/CRMsci	CRMhs
aDNA project	AO_Collection	PE35_Project	HS_Project
Acquisition of sample	HS_Activity		
Initial Sample Processed Sample	AO_Object	E20 Biological_Object S13_Sample	HS_Sample
Sample Processing step	AO_Event	S2_Sample_Taking	HS_Sample_Preparation
Analysis steps Sequencing	AO_Event	S4_Observation/D7_Digital _Machine_Event	HS_Analysis
Protocol used in a step of the workflow		E29_Design_or_Procedure	HS_Protocol
Dataset generated by a processing step of the workflow		PE18_Dataset	HS_Dataset
excavation from		A9_Archaeological_Excavat	

aDNA workflow main entities	AO-Cat	CRM/CRMpe/CRMsci	CRMhs
where the sample is obtained (contextual info)		ion	

Table 3: Main entities of the aDNA AP and alignment with CRMhs.

Each aDNA project is modelled as an AO_Collection that refers to a [PE35_Project, HS_Project] and supports several different activities. A core activity is the acquisition of the samples to be used in the experiments. An acquisition activity (E8_Acquisition) consists of one or more sample-taking activities (S2_Sample_Taking, HS_Sample_Preparation) that deals with each distinct sample. For each sample basic information was recorded about the archaeological excavation within which the sample was found. The sample itself is modelled as [S13_Sample, HS_Sample] and also, in the case of aDNA, as E20_Biological_Object.

The archaeological excavation is modelled as an A9_Archaeological_Excavation class with basic information about the archaeological excavation, including the responsible entity, the broad location where it took place, the time period to which it refers, and the findings of interest from where the sample(s) are taken.

Having acquired the appropriate samples there are a number of steps that are followed in a particular protocol. Each step was modelled as an [S4_Observation, HS_Analysis] along with any associated basic information regarding the person who processed the sample, the place where it was processed, the date, the protocol upon which it is based, any input parameters in use and of course, the results.

4.4 Application Profile for Inscriptions

The development of CRMtex, the ontological model for inscriptions, marks, graffiti and other textual entities continued throughout the duration of ARIADNEplus and led to the definition of a complete application profile fully compatible with AO-Cat. The main features of CRMtex and its use in ARIADNEplus were illustrated as a case study in section 7 of D4.2. This section presents the most recent updates of the model and its harmonisations with AO-Cat.

One of the most important features that needs to be underlined in the study of ancient handwritten documents is the tight relationship between the text and its physical support. CRMtex allows to distinguish these two levels (i.e., the inscription and its carrier object) by using the CIDOC CRM E22 Man-Made Object class to describe physical objects such as coins, vases and monuments bearing written texts, and by providing a specific class (TX1 Written Text) to model the carried texts and all their peculiar features. The CIDOC CRM property P56 is found on is used to directly relate the text to its support. Compatibility with AO-Cat is established by automatically defining all the instances of E22 and TX1 as instances of the AO-Object class at the same time. This allows the inheritance of all the related AO-Cat properties and the proper incorporation of textual information in the ARIADNEplus Catalogue (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: CRMtex, CIDOC CRM and AO-Cat modelling of a Medieval coin bearing inscriptions on the obverse and reverse sides (from Cyprus Institute archives).

CRMtex also provides classes and properties to represent the languages, scripts and alphabets used for their writing (TX3 Writing System), and to model the operations typically performed by scholars to investigate and study the texts, such as reading (TX11 Reading), deciphering and understanding (TX5 Text Recognition), translating and transcribing (TX6 Transliteration) it. These new entities are also fully compatible with CIDOC CRM and AO-Cat (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: CRMtex, CIDOC CRM and AO-Cat modelling of the various investigation operations (i.e., reading, understanding, transliterating and translating) of an ancient Greek inscription from Cyprus, bearing an epigram of the ancient poet Myrto (Cyprus Institute archives).

For the investigation of specific portions of text and of the interconnections existing between a text and its parts, CRMtex also provides additional classes allowing the identification of specific textual components that scholars need to focus on for study purposes, such as text segments, columns, sections and paragraphs, but also single words or letters.

4.5 Application Profile for Mortuary Data

Mortuary archaeology studies human remains in their archaeological context. As described in the Mortuary Data Application Profile (Aspöck, Felicetti, Theodoridou 2022), it ‘consists of a series of research activities and analyses carried out either directly on mortuary evidence (archaeological evidence containing human remains or contexts that are interpreted to relate to the disposal of the dead), and/or on documentation and finds (human remains, objects, samples) from such contexts. Mortuary evidence provides information firstly about ways of disposal of the corpse, past funerary practices, other practices that involved human remains; secondly, mortuary data is used as a proxy for many aspects of past societies, such as identities, migration, social complexity, landscape and memory, beliefs, art and craft, technologies.’

Mortuary data may be contained in different types of datasets (see D14.1). The mortuary data application profile was developed primarily to facilitate deep integration of databases that aggregate burial data, i.e. item-level data integration. The test data was cemetery databases from the early medieval period (Haperen 2017), as they describe very regular evidence that lends itself for item-level integration - in contrast to mortuary data from many other periods.

The mortuary data AP was structured according to the typical entities and hierarchical structure of early medieval cemetery databases (see Figure 7 and Figure 8): Site (cemetery or other site types containing mortuary deposits); feature (different types of graves, ditches, pits and other features); mortuary deposit (the deposit of human remains and other finds, including containers and furniture); finds (human remains, artefacts, animal remains, samples).

Each of the four levels has properties to answer the main query types used by the ARIADNE Portal: When? Where? What? To make the AP easier to use, the mapping were structured according to these questions. For a semantically rich description of mortuary deposits (i.e. more on the ‘What?’) that would allow integration on the item-level the ARIADNEplus ontology was not sufficient so additional classes and properties from the CIDOC-CRM (Doerr 2003) were used:

1. CIDOC CRM – The base model, version 6.2.1 8 (<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/>)
2. CRMsci – Scientific observation model, version 1.2.2 (<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/crmsci/>)
3. CRMarchaeo – Excavation model, version 1.4.1 (<https://www.cidoc-crm.org/crmarchaeo/>)

A detailed list of all the CIDOC CRM mappings used for the mortuary data AP has been presented in D14.1, Section 6. The first version of the Mortuary Data AP was then tested and revised (see below, section 6) and the final version published on Zenodo (Aspöck, Felicetti, Theodoridou 2022). In the following sections the AP is summarised according to its classes.

Modelling the relativity of data: E13_Attribute_Assignment

An assignment event (E13_Attribute_Assignment) was used to document the attribution of types and the observations made are dependent to a degree on the methods used and the views of the person who created/curated the database. For the test data 'In Touch With The Dead' (Van Haperen 2017) the E13 Attribute Assignment event was used to document that the data reflects the view of Martine van Haperen:

```
P140i_was_attributed_by -> E13_Attribute_Assignment -> P14_carried_out_by -> E21_Person = "Martine van Haperen"
```

Site (Cemetery): E27_Site / AO_Collection

Site is the top-level entity and was mapped as E27_Site, defined as relatively immobile material items and features at a particular location, and applies to archaeological sites. It is a more precise mapping than E26 Physical Feature or E18 Physical Thing, which are both superclasses of E27 Site (see below, mapping of THANADOS database). To make a (cemetery) database visible in the ARIADNE portal, it has to be mapped to the AO-Cat too. A cemetery database is mapped as an AO_Collection.

Sites and monuments data is also mapped. This includes information about the name, identifier, geographical extent and its date range (expressed via the ARIADNE properties *has_title*, *has_identifier*, *has_space_region*, *has_time_interval*) and in most cases there will also be classification of a site (e.g. a cremation cemetery, an inhumation cemetery). Additional specifications for 'What?' – i.e. information on the type of cemetery or other type of information – is mapped as *has_type* -> AO_Concept. The original vocabulary of the database is integrated into the infrastructure via the property 'has_native_subject' which means it can later be queried via the ARIADNE interface. Native site types have to be mapped to the Arts and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) (<http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300387004>) which has been chosen as the common thesaurus of the ARIADNEplus infrastructure.

Feature (Context, grave, ...): A8_Stratigraphic_Unit / AO_Collection

In our test database, the table containing information on the individual features of the cemetery (mostly inhumation graves, but also pits, ditches, animal graves, sometimes buildings) was called 'ContextInfo'. In other datasets this field may be called 'feature', 'context' or 'grave'. We mapped this information as an 'A8_Stratigraphic_Unit', as generally these include physical features that consist archaeologically of A2 Stratigraphic Volume Units and A3 Stratigraphic Interfaces. Analogously to information on a site, the information on the feature must be mapped to the AO_Cat to make it visible in the ARIADNE portal. It was therefore mapped as an AO_Collection.

Information about the name, identifier, geographical extent, date range and type of feature is mapped to the same type of information relating to a site. Information about the measurements of a grave (width, length, depth) appear widely and are frequently used to infer information about the 'investment' in the burial of a dead person. For example, a mapping says that a stratigraphic unit contains remains of an object of the type 'grave pit', that is a stratigraphic interface with the dimension (width, length, depth) of 'xx':

AP15_is_or_contains_remains_of

-> AO_Object

->A3_Stratigraphic_Interface -> P2_has_type -> E55_Type = "grave pit"

->P43_has_dimension -> E54_Dimension

-> P2_has_type -> E55_Type = "width"

-> P90_has_value ->rdf-schema#Literal

The dating of the reopening of a grave was mapped in the following way: the feature was present at another event. In this case it was present at the activity 'reopening', which was an event that took place in the time from (year) / until (year):

P12i_was_present_at -> E7_Activity -> P2_has_type -> E55_Type 'reopening'

Mortuary deposit (burial): A8_Stratigraphic_Unit / AO_Collection

In our test dataset, there was no separate entity for each mortuary deposit (i.e. burial of human remains), but the finds were described as part of the features. However, many cemetery databases will have entities for the individual deposits, which is important as frequently there is more than one burial in a grave – even in the early medieval period. Usually, large finds such as coffins or other furniture related to an individual burial is described as part of this entity.

Measurements of a coffin or other grave furniture may be mapped relative to the mapping of the size of the 'grave pit' (see above). For example, a stratigraphic unit contains an object of the type 'coffin', that is an A2 Stratigraphic Volume Unit which had the dimensions length and width.

Finds (grave goods, artefacts): AO_Object & E22_Man-made-Object / AO_Individual_Data_Resource

Both were used: E22 Man-made-object as well as AO_Object, as the class AO_Object allows to use all the AO-Cat properties. AO_Object is a subclass of E18 Physical thing. The 'When?' and 'Where' questions were mapped relative to the other entities. To make the data visible in the ARIADNE portal the finds were mapped as an AO_Individual_Data_Resource.

Information on the material of an artefact is frequently used to make inferences (e.g. about social status, identity) and mapped (P45_consists_of -> E57_Material). The number of objects of a certain type may also be relevant:

P43_has_dimension-> E54_Dimension -> P2_has_type -> E55_Type='numeral'

-> P90_has_value -> rdf-schema#Literal.

Depending on the research question, many other classifications of artefacts may be made, for example 'intentionally damaged', 'Christian symbolism'.

Finds: Human remains, animal remains: AO_Concept & E20_Biological_Object

Relative to assignments by archaeologists (and finds specialists), all data on human (or animal) remains are also attributed to a person via an attribute assignment (E13):

P140i_was_attributed_by -> E13_Attribute_Assignment -> *P14_carried_out_by* -> E21_Person = "Name of Biological Anthropologist"

Properties designated by the biological anthropologist, such as sex, age at death, pathologies, preservation, position of the skeleton will be mapped as types:

has_type -> AO_Concept -> has_type -> E55_Type ['Sex', 'AgeAtDeath', ...]

Figure 7: Graphical representation of structure and selected parts of the mortuary data AP.

Figure 8: Graphical representation of structure and selected parts of the mortuary data AP.

5 Vocabularies and gazetteers

Work on multilingual vocabularies overlaps with work for WP5 on vocabulary integration via mappings from partner vocabularies to the Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) and via the PeriodO framework for temporal periods (see also WP5 Deliverables and the User Manual for the ARIADNEplus Data Aggregation Pipeline). Following strategies developed in the first phase of the ARIADNE project, the AAT plays a central role as a vocabulary hub for the ARIADNEplus data aggregation process and as a multilingual vocabulary. In the temporal dimension, PeriodO serves as a repository for the named periods relevant to (and contributed by) each partner with corresponding spatial region and numeric year spans. Multilingual concepts from Wikidata with mappings to the AAT have also been extracted via SPARQL queries as an additional multilingual resource.

5.1 AAT

The main focus of the multilingual capability is the AAT. The AAT (AAT 2022) can be considered more a knowledge base with a rich set of attributes and links than a simple vocabulary. A semantic network connects the different facets of the AAT. The scope extends further than the name implies, and it has broad coverage of most archaeological concepts that affords its use a vocabulary mapping hub. Sometimes the mapping is a ‘broad mapping’ relationship to a more general concept in the AAT, still useful for concept search purposes over the aggregated ARIADNEplus data. and which can be used in conjunction with more detailed partner source vocabulary. The AAT is actively maintained and there is a longstanding programme to make the vocabulary more multilingual, multicultural, and inclusive (Harpring 2022).

Consider the domain specific partner concept “CEMETERY”, mapped to the AAT --- skos:exactMatch aat:300266755 “cemeteries”. This has preferred labels in different languages: "cemeteries"@en, "campos santos"@es, "campi santi"@it, "cimetières"@fr, "begraafplaatsen"@nl, "Friedhof"@de

It has alternate labels: "cemetery"@en, "campos santos (cemeteries)"@en, "campo santo (cemetery)"@en, "campo santo"@es, "campo santo"@it, "cimetière"@fr, "cœmeterium (cemeteries)"@la, "camposanto (cemetery)"@en, "camposanto"@it, "begraafplaats"@nl, "Friedhöfe"@de

Further, the AAT (poly)hierarchical structure includes narrower AAT concepts (more specific) than cemeteries, which will also have multilingual preferred / alternate terms:

catacombs, columbaria (cemeteries), graveyards, lawn cemeteries, memorial parks, necropolises, Reihengräberfelder, churchyards, cineraria (cemeteries), military cemeteries (veteran cemeteries), national cemeteries, pet cemeteries, potter’s fields, war cemeteries

These can also be taken advantage of to widen the multilingual vocabulary. For example, they can form the basis for concept-based query expansion as provided in the ARIADNEplus Portal (and see [Binding *et al.* 2019] for an ARIADNE project case study).

Mappings are inherently reusable as they describe semantic relationships between persistent concepts relating to the domain but are not restricted in scope to a particular dataset. Therefore, 6,400+ existing vocabulary mappings from the previous ARIADNE project were reused. These were then revised and supplemented as appropriate to account for changes and additions that may have occurred to the source data in the interim period. Additional mappings were also produced by the new ARIADNEplus data providers. At the time of writing, the project has collated 19,220 mappings from multilingual native vocabulary terms to AAT concepts. A further 598,584 mappings from multilingual terms to AAT concepts have been extracted from Wikidata.

5.2 PeriodO

PeriodO (2022) is an international collaborative effort to create a freely available, multilingual, linked data reference gazetteer to describe historical and archaeological named periods (Shaw *et al.* 2016). It has been adopted by ARIADNEplus to provide a framework for the project's space-time gazetteer and periodisation system. The use of PeriodO is integrated into the implementation of the Aggregation Workflow and the ARIADNEplus Portal.

“PeriodO is a [public domain](#) gazetteer of scholarly definitions of historical, art-historical, and archaeological periods. It eases the task of linking among datasets that define periods differently. It also helps scholars and students see where period definitions overlap or diverge.” [PeriodO 2022]

Partners upload their relevant standard sets of named periods into a PeriodO ‘authority’. Every individual period definition associates the period name with a particular spatial coverage and with a start date and end date, plus other metadata including a bibliographic reference for the source of the definition. Periods and authorities have ‘permalink’ identifiers (URIs) so they can be clearly and unambiguously referenced.

For example, the identifier <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4scv9> defines the period “Haut Moyen Âge” (High Middle Age) within the authority <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4> “PACTOLS chronology periods used in DOLIA data”.

ARIADNEplus adopted the published period definitions used in ARIADNE (revised and supplemented where necessary). Additional period authorities from new ARIADNEplus partners were contributed to PeriodO (with assistance in partner use of PeriodO from USW). At the time of writing there are 18 PeriodO authorities published for ARIADNE and ARIADNEplus, containing over 1,900 period definitions. The authorities in use include:

Provider	PeriodO authority	
ARIADNE Project	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66	ARIADNE Consortium. ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015.
AIAC	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p06v8w4	AIAC and L - P : Archaeology. FASTI - Home. 2004.
DANS-KNAW	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0pqptc	Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed. Het Archeologisch Basisregister (ABR). 1992.
IAVP	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02kbfm	Institute of Archaeology "Vasile Pârvan". Romanian Dobruja Periodization for ARIADNEplus. 2020.
INRAP	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4	INRAP: Institut National de Recherches Archeologiques Preventive. PACTOLS chronology periods used in DOLIA data. 2021.
KHM-UO	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p04h98q	Norsk arkeologisk leksikon. 2005.
UoY-ADS	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0kh9ds	Heritage Data. Heritage Data Linked Data Vocabularies for Cultural Heritage. 2014.
UoY-ADS	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0xxt6t	Historic Environment Scotland. Scottish Archaeological Periods & Ages (ScAPA). 2018.
ROCEEH	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0s2rwk	The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans (ROCEEH) research center. ROCEEH Out of Africa Database (ROAD). 2020.
ARUP	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0wctqt	Martin Kuna and David Novák. AMCR Periods Vocabulary. 2019.
PAS	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0gjgrs	Portable Antiquities Scheme. Periods used on the database. 2003.
ASU	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02kkd9 http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p03dr36	David R. Abbott. Extensive and Long-Term Specialization: Hohokam Ceramic Production in the Phoenix Basin, Arizona. 2009-07. David R. Abbott et al. Calculating Hohokam Domestic Architecture Building Costs to Test an Environmental Model of Architectural Changes. 2019-04.
CARARE	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p06hps8	Carlin, Neil et al. Archaeological periods for the island of Ireland. 2022.

Provider	PeriodO authority	
LNEC	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0cwscs	DB-HERITAGE project. DB-HERITAGE historical periods. 2021.
NARA	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0g8mw8	Agency for Cultural Affairs, Government of Japan. Exhibition of Excavations in the Japanese Archipelago 2020. 2020.
SND	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0vn2fr	Historiska museet. Sök i samlingarna (beta). 2011.
THANADOS	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0cwwzn	Stefan Eichert and Nina Richards. THANADOS - The Anthropological and Archaeological Database of Sepultures. 2022.

Table 4: PeriodO authorities used in ARIADNEplus.

6 Assessing the CRM extensions

6.1 Overview

The assessment of the CRM extensions included testing integrated data from the fields of numismatics, epigraphies and mortuary archaeology. A semantic search demonstrator was built to query and test the numismatic and epigraphic data integrated to the item-level. The mapping of Thanados database to the infrastructure was used to test the mortuary data AP.

In the following subsections we present the semantic search demonstrator and the three use cases and the results of the experiments.

6.2 Semantic search demonstrator

In order to assess the validity of the work done in implementing the ARIADNEplus ontology and the creation of application profiles for the archaeological subdomains (mainly carried out in WP4, T4.4, but also in WP2, 5, 12 and 14), it needed to be possible to answer complex research questions on the integrated semantic data. The ARIADNEplus portal, as described in detail in D12.4 *Final report on data integration*, offers a browsing facility, allowing the visual exploration of the ARIADNEplus Knowledge Base according to the primary semantic categories defined in AO-Cat at the level of AO_Collections and AO_Individual_Data_Resources. In order to assess the ARIADNEplus ontology the ARIADNEplus Knowledge Base needed to be exploited at a deeper item-level according to extra semantic categories defined by the Application Profiles for the archaeological subdomains. Two use cases, numismatics and epigraphies, were selected and a demonstrator of a powerful user-friendly semantic searching interface was implemented, the main characteristic of which is the user's support for a flexible exploratory search over the semantic graph, where users can transparently construct their semantic queries being guided by the system and based on the knowledge of intermediate query results.

The search interface is built on the ResearchSpace platform. ResearchSpace is an open source collaborative environment for humanities and cultural heritage research using knowledge representation and Semantic Web technologies, developed by the British Museum (see <http://researchspace.org> and <https://github.com/researchspace/researchspace> for details).

The platform enables the rapid development of semantic applications providing a mechanism for easy building of web pages. The platform comprises custom HTML5 web components, named the Semantic Components, designed to operate on the result of SPARQL queries being executed over the knowledge graph. These components are structures that expose configurable parameters, e.g. setting the input query of the component, the format of a result, the html presentation of the final output, etc.

An important component of the platform is the Semantic Search component. This component applies the idea of the Fundamental Categories and Relationships (FCs/FRs) to create a semantic query builder. In short, an FC, in a simple implementation, can be considered as a Class of entities (usually of a high level). FRs are generic semantic relations among the FCs. So, the key process is the definition of proper FRs that associate two FCs, as shortcut relations that hide the complexity of the

corresponding graph patterns that connect the instances of these categories. Like all semantic relations, FRs are directed links from the source-FC to the target-FC. Based on this idea, the Semantic Search interface allows for the definition of categories and relations, provided to the users for building their semantic queries (Tzobanaki 2012).

In the ARIADNEplus Semantic Search demonstrator, two searchable categories are provided, *Coin* and *Inscription* and their relations to other categories such as Material, Appellation, Terminology, Place, Actor, Document, Intention Attribute (see Table 5). The list of relations is by no means complete. It is an indicative list of what can be implemented.

Coin	Inscription	
consists of		Material
has obverse inscription has reverse inscription		Inscription
has name has title		Appellation
has denomination		Terminology
was produced at	Refers to	Place
was produced by issued by published by	was written by refers to read by	Actor
is referred to by		Document
	was intended for purpose was intended for event	Intention
	has language has type is encoded by	Attribute

Table 5: ARIADNEplus Semantic Search categories and relations

The basic event flow for building queries, through the UI, is:

1. User: Selects a category to search for instances. This is considered the source-Category of a Relation.
2. System: Shows the user a set of all the associated target-Categories, regarding the previously selected source-Category.
3. User: Selects a category. This is considered the target-Category of the available Relation(s).

4. System: Offers the user a set of all available Relations that can associate the source and the target-Category.
5. User: Selects a Relation.
6. System: Asks about either of the following answers, in order to complete the query statement:
 - i. which instance of the target-Category is preferred in the search process. The user at this point has to select a particular resource, found by one of the following options provided by the system:
 - a type-ahead mechanism for any type of labelled resources;
 - a tree selector mechanism, suitable for concepts and place-names hierarchies;
 - a map-selector mechanism, suitable for places with known coordinates;
 - a calendar mechanism for date values and timespans;

or,

- ii. how the target-Category can be further related to other categories and repeat steps B to F using the target-Category as source for another relation. NB: This step is not currently activated in the demo.

During the query building process described above, each time a new query statement is constructed and added to the main query, the latter is executed and the result is shown to the user. Then options are offered to the user for filtering the result according to the relations of the retrieved instances provided by the system. At this point, the user can view the number of retrieved instances grouped under a particular value of each relation, and make a selection of what cases are to be filtered in the final result. In the following subsections we present the two use cases implemented with this demonstrator; section 6.2.1 describes the field of numismatics while section 6.2.2 describes the field of inscriptions.

6.2.1 Assessing CRM with numismatic data

The experimental semantic search demonstrator integrated numismatic data from three providers (Table 6) and allows the formulation of queries across the three datasets. Details about the data and their mappings are provided in D12.4.

Provider	Collection
The Cyprus Institute	Cypriot Medieval Coins History and Culture https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/resource/6d82f84bb28354b78abd2e0ebc796e1630861fa20d3ad779f2578d2edbc3edda
British Museum	Portable Antiquities Scheme Database https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/resource/2d3aeaaa92123ec468b4aac10b0861fa5ac728406b8185faa80a4473

Provider	Collection
	5627b40b
Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	Ancient coins found in Europe (AFE-RGK) https://ariadne-portal-staging.d4science.org/resource/9977a0b3091521665c151e3a72bd97b1b428b561072f3e21920044fbe22af5fb

Table 6: Numismatic data collections.

The datasets are modelled using AO-Cat and additionally CIDOC CRM core and nomisma.org, an international, collaborative project that provides stable digital representations of numismatic concepts according to the principles of Linked Open Data (<https://nomisma.org/>). Figure 9 presents the formulation of the query “Find coins that consist of bronze”. A typical problem that nomisma.org helps to solve is the diverse terminology used in the different datasets. For example, in the three datasets used, the terms *AE*, *AE or Billon*, *AE(?)*, *bronze* and *copper alloy* are used to represent the material of a coin. By mapping these terms to the common <http://nomisma.org/id/ae> term (Figure 10) we guarantee that a search both with native and nomisma.org terms will succeed. Similarly, nomisma.org can be used to integrate other fields such as denominations and mints. The result of this query is 198 coins from all three datasets. 169 coins are from the British Museum, 15 from the Deutsches Archäologisches Institut and 14 from The Cyprus Institute (Figure 11). We can see parts of the results of the query in Figure 12 and Figure 13. Finally, Figure 14 displays the details of a particular coin.

AriadnePlus - ResearchSpace Platform

Home / SemanticSearch

Coin consists of Material cancel

Find a Material:

- Bronze
 - AE
 - AE or Billon
 - AE(?)
 - Bronze
 - Copper alloy
- Silver
 - AR
 - Silber
 - Silver
- Gold
 - Gold

Cancel Select

Figure 9: Formulation of the query “Find coins that consist of bronze”.

[Browse IDs](#)
[About](#)
[Who We Are](#)
[Research Tools](#)
[Documents](#)

Bronze (Material, Concept)

Canonical URI: <http://nomisma.org/id/ae>

Labels

Preferred Label Bronze (*en*), Bronze (*de*), Bronze (*fr*), Bronzo (*it*), Χαλκός (*el*), bronce (*es*) [Additional labels](#) ▶

Definitions

en 'AE' is the numismatic abbreviation for bronze or any copper alloy.

Relations

Exact Match <http://collection.britishmuseum.org/id/thesauri/x10627>

Exact Match <http://d-nb.info/gnd/4146667-6>

Exact Match <http://dbpedia.org/resource/Bronze>

Exact Match <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300010957>

Exact Match <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q34095>

Exact Match <https://ikmk.smb.museum/ndp/material/2>

Exact Match <https://www.freebase.com/m/01brf>

Concept Scheme <http://nomisma.org/id/>

Figure 10: 'Bronze' as described in nomisma.org.

▼ published by

Search actors...

- British Museum (169)
- Deutsches Archäologisches Institut (15)
- The Cyprus Institute (14)

Figure 11: Publishers of the coins that include Bronze as a material.

AriadnePlus - ResearchSpace Platform

Home / SemanticSearch

Find: Coins CONSISTS OF Bronze

Coin consists of Material Bronze remove

found 198 matches

Grid Table Carousel Chart

subject	denomination	publisher	material	obverse_inscription	reverse_inscription
Coin 514815	Nummus (AE 1 - AE 4)	British Museum	Copper alloy		
Coin 515099	Dupondius or as	British Museum	Copper alloy		
Coin 514992	Radiate or nummus	British Museum	Copper alloy		
Coin 514194	Nummus (AE 1 - AE 4)	British Museum	Copper alloy		
Coin 514473	Nummus (AE 1 - AE 4)	British Museum	Copper alloy		
Coin 515102	Nummus (AE 1 - AE 4)	British Museum	Copper alloy		
Coin 514396	Radiate (antoninianus)	British Museum	Copper alloy		
Coin 515133	Nummus (AE 1 - AE 4)	British Museum	Copper alloy		
Coin 514536	Farthing (Copper alloy)	British Museum	Copper alloy		
Coin 1987-01-02	Denier	The Cyprus Institute	AE or Billon	DVX IANVE	CIVIT FAMAG
Coin 1996-02-05	AE	The Cyprus Institute	AE	HEERICVS	REX CYPRI
Coin 1985-03-07	Bezant	The Cyprus Institute	AE	PRO REGNI CYPRI PRESSIDIO 1570	VENETORV FIDES INVIOIABILIS BISANTE I F
Coin 1999-03-90	Bezant	The Cyprus Institute	AE	PRO REGNI CYPRI PRESSIDIO 1570	VENETORV FIDES INVIOIABILIS BISANTE I F(?)
Coin 1996-06-02	Denier	The Cyprus Institute	AE	REX GVIDO	IERUSALEM,REX GVIDO
Coin 1999-03-89	Sizin	The Cyprus Institute	AE	SANCTVS MARCVS VENET	PETRVS LAVREDA DVX

Figure 12: Partial result set of the query “Find coins that consist of bronze.”

AriadnePlus - ResearchSpace Platform

Home / SemanticSearch

Find: Coins CONSISTS OF Bronze

Coin consists of Material Bronze remove

found 198 matches

Grid Table Carousel Chart

subject	denomination	publisher	material	obverse_inscription	reverse_inscription
Coin 1992-01-04	Carzi	The Cyprus Institute	AE(?)	IACOBVS	IERVSALEM
Coin 1999-07-04	Denier	The Cyprus Institute	AE	PIERE ROI DEI	RVSL ED CHP
Coin 1988-08-02	AE	The Cyprus Institute	AE	HENRICVS	REX
Coin 1999-05-04	AE	The Cyprus Institute	AE	HENRICVS	REX CIPRI
Coin 1989-03-41	Sizin	The Cyprus Institute	AE	IACOBUS DEI GRAIAX	ERXX IHERUSALEM (20th king of Jerusalem)
Coin 1996-01-01	Sizin	The Cyprus Institute	AE	IACUS DEI REX	IERUSALEM C
Coin 1985-03-08	Bezant	The Cyprus Institute	AE	PRO REGNI CYPRI PRESSIDIO 1570	VENETORV FIDES INVIOIABILIS BISANTE I
Coin 1999-03-91	Bezant	The Cyprus Institute	AE	[PIRO REGNI CYPRI PRESSIDIO 1570	V[E]NETORV FIDES INVIOIABILIS BISANTE I
Coin 16201	Sestertius	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	Bronze		
Coin 16169	Sestertius	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	Bronze		
Coin 16643	As / Dupondius	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	Bronze		
Coin 16196	Sestertius	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	Bronze		
Coin 16628	Sestertius	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	Bronze		
Coin 16636	As	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	Bronze		
Coin 16203	Follis	Deutsches Archäologisches Institut	Bronze		

Figure 13: Partial result set of the query “Find coins that consist of bronze.”

AriadnePlus - ResearchSpace Platform

Home / Coin 1999-03-90g

Coin 1999-03-90

URI: <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/locat/035f44b6-c932-3af4-8881-0f98a2d6d76>

Type: AO_Object, E22_Man-Made_Object

About Record Source

Property	Value
has title	AE Bezant, Marc Antonio Bragadino, after 1570
consists of	AE
has denomination	Bezant
was produced by	Production was carried out by Mint Famagusta(?) took place at Spatial Region Point Famagusta(?), and was motivated_by Issuing of coin 1999-03-90
has dimension	06:00 h axis
has dimension	29.50 mm diameter
has dimension	4.59 gm weight
bears feature	Obverse Inscription: PRO REGNI CYPRI PRESSIDIO 1570
bears feature	Reverse Inscription: VENETORV FIDES INVIOLABILIS BISANTE I F(?)
has time interval	VENETIAN period from 1489 until 1571-01-01T00:00:00.000Z
has time interval	VENETIAN period from 1489 until 1571
has type	Coin
is referred to by	Bibliography Pitsillides 1976, 11-15; Michaelidou 2002, 258-259 & 262.
has identifier	1999-03-90
label	Coin 1999-03-90

Figure 14: Details of Coin 1999-03-90.

Furthermore, to assess the suitability of the models for integrated queries, we ran indicative queries on https://ariadne.d4science.org/group/ariadneplus_lab/graphdb which is the SPARQL endpoint of the ARIADNEplus Knowledge Base. Table 7 presents the queries, the respective SPARQL query and the results.

Namespaces used:

PREFIX rdf: <<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>>
 PREFIX rdfs: <<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>>
 PREFIX skos: <<http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>>
 PREFIX aocat: <<https://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/resource/ao/cat/1.1/>>
 PREFIX crm: <<http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>>
 PREFIX crmtex: <<http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/crmtex/>>
 PREFIX nomisma: <<http://nomisma.org/ontology/>>

Query	Sparql	No of results Publishers
Get a list of mints	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?mint ?mintlabel WHERE { { ?resource aocat:has_ARIADNE_subject ?concept. ?concept skos:prefLabel "Coin"@en. ?resource rdfs:label ?label; aocat:is_about ?object. ?object crm:P108i_was_produced_by ?production. ?production crm:P14_carried_out_by ?mint. ?mint rdfs:label ?mintlabel. }}</pre>	51 mints 10 from Cyl 34 from BM 7 from AFE-RGK

Query	Sparql	No of results Publishers
Get a list of denominations	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?denomination ?denlabel WHERE { { ?resource aocat:has_ARIADNE_subject ?concept. ?concept skos:prefLabel "Coin"@en. ?resource rdfs:label ?label; aocat:is_about ?object. ?object crm:P2_has_type ?denomination. ?denomination a nomisma:Denomination; skos:prefLabel ?denlabel. }}</pre>	<p>55 denominations 8 from Cyl 37 from BM 10 from AFE-RGK</p>
Find mints that issued AE or Copper alloy or Bronze coins	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?mint ?mintL WHERE { { ?resource aocat:has_ARIADNE_subject ?concept. ?concept skos:prefLabel "Coin"@en. ?resource rdfs:label ?label; aocat:is_about ?object. ?object crm:P45_consists_of ?material. ?material a crm:E57_Material; skos:prefLabel ?materialL FILTER (?materialL = "Copper alloy"@en ?materialL = "AE"@en ?materialL = "Bronze"@en) ?object crm:P108i_was_produced_by ?production. ?production crm:P14_carried_out_by ?mint. ?mint rdfs:label ?mintL }}</pre>	<p>29 5 from Cyl 21 from BM 3 from AFE-RGK</p> <p>Note that within the ARIADNEplus knowledge base the mapping of native materials to nomisma has not been implemented.</p>
Get the weight and diameter of a coin	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?resource ?weight ?diameter { ?resource aocat:is_about ?object . ?resource aocat:has_ARIADNE_subject ?concept. ?concept skos:prefLabel "Coin"@en. ?object <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/P43_has_dimension> ?dimension . ?object rdfs:label ?label . OPTIONAL { ?object crm:P43_has_dimension ?weightD. ?weightD crm:P2_has_type <https://ariadne- infrastructure.eu/aocat/Concept/AO_Type/weight> . ?weightD crm:P90_has_value ?weightV . ?weightD crm:P91_has_unit/(rdfs:label skos:prefLabel) ?weightU . BIND (CONCAT(STR(?weightV), STR(?weightU)) AS ?weight) } OPTIONAL { ?object <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-</pre>	<p>243 109 from Cyl 134 from AFE_RGK</p>

Query	Sparql	No of results Publishers
	<pre> crm/P43_has_dimension> ?diameterD. ?diameterD crm:P2_has_type <https://ariadne- infrastructure.eu/aocat/Concept/AO_Type/diameter> . ?diameterD crm:P90_has_value ?diameterV . ?diameterD crm:P91_has_unit/(rdfs:label skos:prefLabel) ?diameterU . BIND (CONCAT(STR(?diameterV), STR(?diameterU)) AS ?diameter) }} </pre>	
<p>Get coins with inscriptions (epigraphic data)</p>	<pre> SELECT DISTINCT ?resource ?inscription_type ?inscription WHERE { ?resource aocat:is_about ?object . ?resource aocat:has_ARIADNE_subject ?concept. ?concept skos:prefLabel "Coin"@en. ?object crm:P56_bears_feature ?feature . ?feature a crmtex:TX1_Written_Text . ?feature crm:P2_has_type/skos:prefLabel ?inscription_type . ?feature crm:P3_has_note ?inscription . } </pre>	<p>220 inscriptions 220 from Cyl</p>
<p>Find coins issued by a specific mint</p> <p>https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/aocat/AFE_RGK/Mint/Roma</p> <p>https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/aocat/BMPAS/Mint/Rome</p>	<pre> SELECT DISTINCT ?resource ?mint ?mintL { VALUES ?mint { <https://ariadne- infrastructure.eu/aocat/BMPAS/Mint/Rome> <https://ariadne- infrastructure.eu/aocat/AFE_RGK/Mint/Roma> } ?resource aocat:is_about ?object . ?object crm:P108i_was_produced_by/crm:P14_carried_out_by ?mint . ?mint rdfs:label ?mintL. } </pre>	<p>138 resources 118 from AFE_RGK 20 from BM</p>

Table 7: Indicative coin queries.

6.2.2 Assessing the CRM extensions with epigraphic data

The experimental semantic search demonstrator integrated epigraphic data from Cyl (Table 8: Collections with epigraphic data Table 8) and allows the formulation of queries across the three datasets. Details about the data and their mappings are provided in D12.4.

Provider	Collection
The Cyprus Institute	Cypriot Medieval Coins History and Culture https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/resource/6d82f84bb28354b78abd2e0ebc796e1630861fa20d3ad779f2578d2edbc3edda
The Cyprus Institute	Archaia Kypriaki Grammateia, a corpus of Ancient texts

Table 8: Collections with epigraphic data.

The datasets are modelled using AO-Cat and CRMtex (Inscriptions, marks and graffiti Application Profile, CRMtex v1.1). In modelling inscription information it was possible to verify that CRMtex, AO-Cat and CIDOC CRM are fully aligned and the formulation of integrated item-level queries is possible. Figure 15 presents the formulation of the query “Find inscriptions written by Nicocles” while Figure 14 displays the details of a particular inscription.

The screenshot shows the AriadnePlus - ResearchSpace Platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with "Home / SemanticSearch". Below this, a search query is displayed: "Find: Inscriptions WAS WRITTEN BY Nicocles". The query is broken down into components: "Inscription" (with a small image icon), "was written by", "Actor" (with a person icon), and "Nicocles". A "remove" button is visible next to the query. Below the query, it says "found 3 matches". There are three tabs: "Grid" (selected), "Table", "Carousel", and "Chart". A message states: "Only entities with image representation are shown in the Grid!". Below this, two images of inscriptions are shown. The first image is labeled "Inscription 7f72ef5..." and shows a stone inscription with Greek text. The second image is labeled "Inscription 9c378b2..." and shows two stone inscriptions side-by-side. Below these, two more images of inscriptions are shown, which appear to be different views or fragments of the same inscription.

Figure 15: Exploring Epigraphies in the Research Space platform.

AriadnePlus - ResearchSpace Platform Login

Home / Inscription 7f72ef52-17d9-4324-876c-8b790d30da85 - R.R. 126g

Inscription 7f72ef52-17d9-4324-876c-8b790d30da85 - R.R. 126

URI: <https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/aocat/Object/080D9F9D-3F3F-30CE-A1AC-5A82765BCDA1>

Type: TX1_Written_Text, AO_Object

About Record Source

Property	Value
carries	Linguistic object that has language Ancient Greek and refers to Timarchus
was written by	Nicocles
was read by	A. Voskos
is encoded by	Ancient Greek
is referred to by	Main references of 7f72ef52-17d9-4324-876c-8b790d30da85 - R.R. 126
label	Inscription 7f72ef52-17d9-4324-876c-8b790d30da85 - R.R. 126
has type	Four verses in elegiac meter
has type	Funerary epigram
was intended for	Funerary
was intended for	The community honors the king Nicocles

Figure 16: Display of a specific inscription.

Indicative queries were run on <https://graphdb-test.ariadne.d4science.org/sparql> which is the SPARQL endpoint of the ARIADNEplus Testing Knowledge Base. At the time of the experiments, some of the epigraphic data was not yet loaded on the official Knowledge Base. The collections of The Cyprus Institute (Cyl) about Coins and Inscriptions contain epigraphic information. Table 9 presents the queries, the respective SPARQL and the results.

Namespaces used:

PREFIX rdf: <<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>>
 PREFIX rdfs: <<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>>
 PREFIX skos: <<http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>>
 PREFIX aocat: <<https://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/resource/ao/cat/1.1/>>
 PREFIX crm: <<http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>>
 PREFIX crmtex: <<http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/crmtex/>>
 PREFIX nomisma: <<http://nomisma.org/ontology/>>

Query	SPARQL	No of results Publishers
Get a list of archaeological objects bearing an inscription	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?object ?objectL ?inscr ?inscrL WHERE { { ?resource rdfs:label ?label; aocat:is_about ?object. {?object crm:P56_bears_feature ?inscr; rdfs:label ?objectL. ?inscr rdfs:label ?inscrL. } UNION {?object a crmtex:TX1_Written_Text; rdfs:label ?objectL.} }}</pre>	253 on staging 220 from Cyl coins 33 from Cyl Inscriptions
Get a list of inscriptions written on "White marble" objects	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?object ?objectL WHERE { { ?object a crmtex:TX1_Written_Text. ?object rdfs:label ?objectL. ?object crm:P56i_is_found_on ?support. ?support crm:P45_consists_of ?material. ?material skos:prefLabel "White marble"@en. }}</pre>	14 from Cyl Inscriptions
Get a list of languages and scripts used in the inscriptions.	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?lnote ?snote WHERE { { ?object a crmtex:TX1_Written_Text; rdfs:label ?objectL; crm:P128_carries ?lo. ?lo crm:P72_has_language ?lang. ?lang crm:P3_has_note ?lnote. ?object crmtex:TXP9_is_encoded_by ?script. ?script crm:P3_has_note ?snote. }}</pre>	12 from Cyl Inscriptions
Get a list of scholars who have been involved in the study of inscriptions	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?actor ?actorL WHERE { { ?object a crmtex:TX1_Written_Text; rdfs:label ?objectL; crmtex:TXP10i_was_read_by ?reading. ?reading crm:P14_carried_out_by ?actor. ?actor rdfs:label ?actorL. }}</pre>	1 from Cyl Inscriptions
Find all inscriptions that have a transcription	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?transcr ?transcrL WHERE { { ?object a crmtex:TX1_Written_Text; rdfs:label ?objectL; crmtex:TXP10i_was_read_by ?reading. ?reading crmtex:TXP3i_is_rendered_by ?transcr. #?transcr rdfs:label ?transcrL. }}</pre>	0

Query	SPARQL	No of results Publishers
	}}	
List all the places mentioned in an inscription	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?object ?placeL WHERE {{ ?object a crmtex:TX1_Written_Text; crm:P128_carries ?lo. ?lo crm:P67_refers_to ?place. ?place a crm:E53_Place. ?place rdfs:label ?placeL. }}</pre>	28 from Cyl Inscriptions

Table 9: Indicative inscription queries.

6.3 Assessing the CRM extensions with mortuary data

The first version of the Mortuary Data AP (see D14.1, Section 6) was tested by integrating the ‘THANADOS anthropological and archaeological database of sepultures’ (<https://thanados.net/>) into the ARIADNE Infrastructure. THANADOS is an online application on early medieval cemeteries that is open source and open access. It aims to present all published archaeological and anthropological data on early medieval cemeteries in currently in Austria. The data are stored in a PostgreSQL/PostGIS database and structured according to classes and properties of the core CIDOC CRM (Eichert 2021). THANADOS uses its own vocabulary (<https://thanados.net/vocabulary>). Where available the vocabulary entries are linked to corresponding entries of controlled vocabularies, e.g. Getty Arts and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT), Geonames, Wikidata. An API provides various output formats for the respective entities. In order to harvest data for ARIADNEplus an XML representation of each cemetery with its graves, human remains and finds was developed.

The mapping of the THANADOS data confirmed the adequacy of the mortuary data AP and contributed in its alignment with AO-Cat. The THANADOS mappings revealed that, for the information on graves, mortuary deposits and finds to show in the ARIADNE portal, an additional mapping to AO_Collection (site, feature (grave, pit, etc.), mortuary deposit (burial)) and AO_Individual_Data_Resource (finds) was necessary. These mappings were added to the profile (see section 4.5). The revised version of the Mortuary Data AP (version 1.2) was published on Zenodo (Aspöck, Felicetti, Theodoridou 2022).

Two papers were presented to CHNT Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Technologies on 11th November 2022 in Vienna, Austria reflecting on the this work:

- Aspöck, E., Theodoridou, M., and Felicetti, A. (2022). ‘The ARIADNE Mortuary Data Application Profile’
- Aspöck, E., Eichert, S., Richards, N. and Theodoridou, M. (2022). ‘Integrating data on early medieval graves from different digital re-sources. The ARIADNEplus Mortuary Data Application Profile’

Furthermore, in order to assess the suitability of the models for integrated queries, we ran indicative queries on <https://graphdb-test.ariadne.d4science.org/sparql> which is the SPARQL endpoint of the ARIADNEplus Testing Knowledge Base that includes the THANADOS data. Unfortunately, there were no other relevant datasets available in the knowledge base but it shows as a proof of concept that if the Mortuary AP is applied consistently, integration is feasible. Table 10 presents the questions, the respective SPARQL queries and the results.

Namespaces used:

PREFIX rdf: <<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>>
 PREFIX rdfs: <<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>>
 PREFIX skos: <<http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>>
 PREFIX aocat: <<https://www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/resource/ao/cat/1.1/>>
 PREFIX crm: <<http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/>>
 PREFIX crmtex: <<http://www.cidoc-crm.org/cidoc-crm/crmtex/>>
 PREFIX nomisma: <<http://nomisma.org/ontology/>>

Query	SPARQL	No of results Publishers
Find all graves of children	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?resource ?resourceL ?Height ?Width WHERE { { ?resource aocat:has_ARIADNE_subject ?concept. ?concept skos:prefLabel "Burial"@en. ?resource aocat:has_native_subject/skos:prefLabel "Child"@en; rdfs:label ?resourceL. }}</pre>	442 from THANADOS
Find the width and height of graves of children	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?resource ?resourceL ?Height ?Width WHERE { { ?resource aocat:has_ARIADNE_subject ?concept. ?concept skos:prefLabel "Burial"@en. ?resource aocat:has_native_subject/skos:prefLabel "Child"@en; rdfs:label ?resourceL. {?resource crm:P43_has_dimension ?dimW. ?dimW crm:P2_has_type/skos:prefLabel "Width"@en. ?dimW crm:P90_has_value ?Width.} {?resource crm:P43_has_dimension ?dimH. ?dimH crm:P2_has_type/skos:prefLabel "Height"@en. ?dimH crm:P90_has_value ?Height.} }}</pre>	1 from THANADOS
Find the height of Female skeletons	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?resource ?resourceL ?Height ?Width WHERE { { ?resource aocat:has_ARIADNE_subject ?concept. ?concept skos:prefLabel "Burial"@en. ?resource aocat:has_native_subject/skos:prefLabel "Female"@en. ?resource aocat:has_native_subject/skos:prefLabel "Skeleton"@en; rdfs:label ?resourceL. }}</pre>	2 from THANADOS

Query	SPARQL	No of results Publishers
	<pre> ?resource crm:P43_has_dimension ?dimH. ?dimH crm:P2_has_type/skos:prefLabel "Height"@en. ?dimH crm:P90_has_value ?Height.}}</pre>	
Find which types of artefacts were buried with children	<pre> SELECT DISTINCT ?type WHERE { { ?resource aocat:has_ARIADNE_subject ?concept. ?concept skos:prefLabel "Burial"@en. ?resource aocat:has_native_subject/skos:prefLabel "Child"@en; rdfs:label ?resourceL. ?resource2 aocat:is_part_of ?resource. ?resource2 aocat:has_native_subject/skos:prefLabel ?type. }}</pre>	116 artefacts from THANADOS
List all graves that have been "Disturbed"	<pre> SELECT DISTINCT ?resourceL WHERE { { ?resource aocat:has_ARIADNE_subject ?concept. ?concept skos:prefLabel "Burial"@en. ?resource aocat:has_native_subject/skos:prefLabel ?nsL. FILTER (contains(?nsL,"Disturbed")) ?resource rdfs:label ?resourceL. }}</pre>	288 from THANADOS

Table 10: Indicative mortuary data queries.

7 Conclusions

Overall, the activities of WP14 were carried out successfully and with very good cooperation with other interlinked work packages, such as WP4, 5, and 12.

Activity Dash, integrated into the projects' infrastructure, was used to monitor the aggregation process. 62 active workflows were created and recorded the aggregation progress status of all the data providers. It helped the aggregation team have a clear idea of the different ongoing processes and provided an easy means of communication between the members involved in each workflow.

The development of the application profiles was carried out in close collaboration between the partners of 14.2 and 4.4 and led to the release of four stable fundamental application profiles for the specific research domains of i) inscriptions, marks, graffiti and other textual entities, ii) ancient DNA analysis, iii) heritage science scientific analysis and (iv) mortuary archaeology. The classes and properties that constitute each application profile are borrowed from existing ontological models or derived from them, and are fully compatible with the AO-Cat general model and the CIDOC CRM, which form the backbone of ARIADNEplus.

Work on multilingual vocabularies was carried out in close collaboration with WP5 on vocabulary integration via mappings from partner vocabularies to the Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) and via the PeriodO framework for temporal periods (see also WP5 Deliverables and the User Manual for the ARIADNEplus Data Aggregation Pipeline). AAT plays a central role as a vocabulary hub for the ARIADNEplus data aggregation process and as a multilingual vocabulary. In the temporal dimension, PeriodO serves as a repository for the named periods relevant to (and contributed by) each partner with corresponding spatial region and numeric year spans. Multilingual concepts from Wikidata with mappings to the AAT have also been extracted via SPARQL queries as an additional multilingual resource.

The assessment of the CRM extensions included testing integrated data from the fields of numismatics, epigraphies and mortuary archaeology. A semantic search demonstrator was built to query and test the numismatic and epigraphic data integrated to the item-level. The mapping of the Thanados database to the infrastructure was used to test the mortuary data AP. The experiments proved that AO-Cat, together with the appropriate specific Apps and the extensions of CIDOC CRM provide a solid basis for heterogeneous resource integration, but dedicated VREs are necessary to support query formulation and result presentation.

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